

How close together can an antiparallel magnetic moments free electron pair get, calculation?

See illustration:

Figure 1

Is there a calculation-prediction of the minimum distance separation of an antiparallel electron pair due its like charge repulsion?

There must be an equilibrium between the magnetic attraction and the charge repulsion?

(the two electrons in the illustration, antiparallel magnetic moments N-S and S-N will attract the two electrons together forming a stable pair but at the same time the Coulomb charge repulsion force will keep them separated at a distance d).

Any analytical solution to this problem?

I believe I heard or read somewhere once I cannot recall, that this distance d described in the question is equal to the Reduced Compton Wavelength of the electron $\lambda = \hbar/mc = 3.861\ 592\ 6796(12) \times 10E-13\ m = 386\ fm$, which is also the uncertainty $\Delta\chi$ in this case but I cannot find any analytical solution?

Specifically, the minimum $\Delta\chi$ uncertainty in the position of a free electron at rest is

$\Delta\chi = 0.5 (\hbar/mc) = 0.5\lambda = 193\ fm$ thus half of its reduced Compton wavelength. Notice here that the **Reduced Compton Wavelength** for the electron also written as $\lambda_e = \lambda_e/2\pi$ where λ_e is the **Compton wavelength** of the electron, represents the radius r of the electron's **rest mass field** shown in the attached illustration (blue sphere).

Therefore, any analytical prediction presented as an answer in this question page must have a minimum uncertainty in the separation distance d for an antiparallel pair of electrons set at $d(\text{uncertainty})=2\Delta\chi=\lambda_e=386 \text{ fm}$.

Thus any value prediction must be written as:

$d=\dots\dots\dots$ (193 fm), where the value in the parenthesis indicates the \pm , uncertainty in the prediction.

Note: Definition of the term **rest mass field** of the electron used in this question, is (or equals) a sphere volume of radius the total minimum uncertainty in position $\Delta\chi$ of an electron at rest, $\pm 193 \text{ fm} = 386 \text{ fm}$. Of course the electron particle by known theory is a massive dimensionless point particle.

Calculation:

According to Alexander A. Mikhailichenko (<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/A-Mikhailichenko>) [1] (eq. 8), reference suggested by Prof. Behnam Farid this equilibrium linear distance d where the two forces equalize is:

$$d=\sqrt{6}\lambda_e\sim 2.5\lambda_e$$

where λ_e is the Reduced Compton Wavelength of the electron thus $\lambda_e=386 \text{ fm} = 0.386$ picometers.

Therefore resulting in a final value of linear separation between the two electron's magnetic moments in an electron pair at rest of $d\sim 2.5\times 386=965 \text{ fm}$.

That is $\times 1.25$ the diameter cross-section of the single electron's *rest mass field* (blue sphere in illustration of anti parallel electron pair). Meaning in the separated antiparallel electron pair a whole third electron can fit in between!

Final value adding uncertainty is,

$$\mathbf{d=965 (193) fm.}$$

[1] A.A. Mikhailichenko, TO THE POSSIBILITY OF BOUND STATES BETWEEN TWO ELECTRONS, (n.d.). <https://accelconf.web.cern.ch/ipac2012/papers/weppp031.pdf> (accessed September 26, 2021).